

Bulaestian [почестне] and its analogies in some Ukrainian dialects

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The rite and lexeme /по|ч'естне/ 'preliminary gifting to a bride and groom/hosts during the initial stage of wedding/christening party' exist among the ethnographic group of Ukrainians of Bulaesti village. During the rite of /по|ч'естне/ guests come to a small table; a bottle of wine and a bowl with jam/sweets are on the table. The guests congratulate the bride and groom/hosts, give small money as a gift (this process is referred to as /к'е|дате" на по|ч'естне/). The bride and groom/hosts pour them a glass of wine, offering also jam or sweets for a snack.

This rite is quite typical. However, the lexeme /по|ч'естне/ is more specific. It distinguishes the Bulaestian dialect from its closest relatives of Bukovina.

Thus, the Ukrainian dialects of Kitsman, Gliboka, Kelimentsy, and Sokireany districts of Chernivtsy region use the lexeme *частувати, чистувати* for the meaning 'to make gifts to bride and groom at their wedding'. In contrast, Bulaestian dialect knows /ч'асту|вати^е/ in the meaning 'to pour wine into glasses; to be a cupbearer'.

There is a Ukrainian dialectal form [почестне] that means 'treat'. Boiky's dialect knows *почестне* as a 'part of the donation to the church, which went to priests, local intelligentsia and the poor'. Also, according to a kind message of I. V. Gorofyanuk, Ukrainian dialects of Podolie region know the lexeme *частувати* that means 'to treat guests to wine/alcohol drink at a wedding'. In the southern part of Podolie region (Yampol and Chechel'nitsy districts of Vinnitsa oblast') this rite is known as *почесна*.

Therefore, we see some semantic interference of lexemes [почестне] and *частувати* in the area of Carpathian (Bukovinian and Boiky's, first of all) and Podolian Ukrainian dialects. And, the analogies of Bulaestian /по|ч'естне/ addresses us to the area of Southern Podolian Ukrainian dialects, and not to the area of Bukovinian ones (that are the closest relatives of Bulaestian dialect).